

1 **Characterization of CD68, a differentially expressed gene in HER2+ breast cancer.**

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7 We previously identified CD68 as a component differentially expressed gene in primary tumors from
8 humans with HER2+ breast cancer. We studied here CD68 expression and its inclusion in gene signatures
9 across tissues and cellular settings. CD68 expression was induced by exposure to pristane in mice *in vivo*.
10 CD68 appeared to be a specific differentially expressed target in HER2+ subtype breast cancer because
11 its expression in a wide survey of tissues from multiple organ systems was higher only in normal tissues
12 rather than tumor tissues. CD68 was Fos-inducible. Importantly, an immune regulatory function for CD68
13 was suggested by co-regulation with HLA-E, Ly96 and CD14.
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